

ESTRATEGIAS DE THINK-ALOUD PARA MEJORAR LA HABILIDAD DE LECTURA EN ESTUDIANTES EN EL CENTRO DE IDIOMAS EN LA UNIVERSIDAD TÉCNICA DE BABAHOYO.

ENHANCING READING SKILL ON STUDENTS IN THE LANGUAGE CENTER AT THE TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF BABAHOYO THROUGH THE USE OF THINK-ALOUD STRATEGIES.

AUTORES: Cecilia Isabel Cánepa Muñoz¹

Cecilia Elizabeth Dahik Solis²

Kerly Jazmín Feijoo Rojas³

DIRECCIÓN PARA CORRESPONDENCIA: ccanepa@utb.edu.ec

Fecha de recepción: 22/noviembre/2018

Fecha de aceptación: 06/marzo/2019

RESUMEN

Este caso de estudio pretende mejorar la comprensión lectora utilizando las estrategias Think-Aloud para captar la atención de los estudiantes durante el proceso, así como conocer las estas estrategias que mejoren la comprensión durante el proceso de la lectura de un texto en el idioma inglés. Este estudio fue realizado con dos estudiantes del Centro de Idiomas (CENID) en la Universidad Técnica de Babahoyo en la Provincia de Los Ríos quienes están en el tercer nivel de estudios. Las estudiantes tienen diferentes entornos culturales y de aprendizaje y el hecho de que hayan estado alejadas de los estudios en el CENID entre 2 y 4 meses pudo influir en las dificultades presentadas en este proceso. En la Introducción se detalla este problema de estudio. Luego se presenta una descripción de la metodología y el uso del método mixto para la obtención de datos y análisis de los resultados. Los resultados obtenidos muestran que Think-Aloud mejora la comprensión lectora y la retroalimentación con la autoevaluación motiva la lectura en las estudiantes. Se concluye con una discusión de los resultados y las conclusiones finales de la investigación.

PALABRAS CLAVES: destreza de lectura, proceso de enseñanza aprendizaje, conocimiento previo, estrategia Think-Aloud, autoevaluación, retroalimentación.

¹ Teacher, Technical University of Babahoyo, E-mail: ccanepa@utb.edu.ec, Babahoyo, Los Ríos, Ecuador

² Teacher, Technical University of Babahoyo, E-mail: cdahikth@utb.edu.ec, Babahoyo, Los Ríos, Ecuador

³ Teacher, Technical University of Babahoyo, E-mail: kfejoo@utb.edu.ec, Babahoyo, Los Ríos, Ecuador

ABSTRACT

This case study aims to enhance reading skill using the think-aloud strategies during the reading process to know how these strategies catch students' attention to read, and how the think-aloud process enables the improvement of this skill in the teaching-learning process. This research was conducted with two students of the CENID language center at the Technical University of Babahoyo in Los Rios Province, who are in the third level and show different language and cultural backgrounds. The fact that they were out of the CENID between two and four months could produce some difficulties in the process of reading comprehension. In the introduction is specified the information about this problem of study in detail. the methodology includes a description of the elements to be used in the process of data collection and the analysis of results through the implementation of the mixed methods. The results suggest that Think-Aloud upgrade the reading skill and feedback through self-assessment increase motivation. Lastly, it is concluded with a discussion of the results and the conclusions.

KEY WORDS: reading skills, the teaching-learning process, prior knowledge, think-aloud strategies, self-assessment, feedback

INTRODUCCION

The following case study was conducted with the purpose to compare the differences between two students' reading skills, who have different language and cultural backgrounds to provide an opportunity to enhance the teaching of reading implementing think-aloud strategies in this process.

Reading skill is a challenge for students and teachers due to it is considered boring and teachers count with few techniques to improve and motivate them in reading classes. Some possible causes for this situation are the students' reluctance to read even in their native language, students' social, cultural and language background which influence the way a learner participate and is motivated to work in class, prior knowledge has a huge impact since students who come from schools where English was taught in a little will have less knowledge to be activated to get the following learning , lack of application of reading strategies which are an important part in the form the students learn and acquire the language, and so on. Thus, it is quite important as teachers get in our hands the tools which would help to face these situations and make possible that learners improve reading comprehension skills, so this study deserves to be studied in a deeper research to apply the most accurate strategies in the reading process.

Through the development of this study, the students will be known as Student A and Student B as pseudonyms. Both students belong to the pre-intermediate level, which corresponds to the third level of the English Modules. Both students are from Babahoyo and study at the University of Babahoyo. This case study was developed at the CENID (in Spanish Centro de Idiomas), this is the Language Center where the students get a certification to continue doing their thesis.

Student A is a 20-year girl, who lives on the outskirts of Babahoyo. She is in the third semester of Obstetrics. She studied in a public school where English is taught five hours per week. Her father is a farmer, and her mother is a homemaker. She has two sisters who still are in High School. Her English studies were very limited since the Teaching of English in public schools is done under severe conditions like large classes, where the teachers cannot develop the productive skills accurately. Student A has completed two levels from the English Modules, but she returned to study after four months, so she has some difficulties with vocabulary, some grammatical structure, but especially with the reading skill due to during this time she has not practiced what she had learned in the English modules.

This student was chosen because she presents much more difficulty with reading comprehension than the other students from the group. It could be evidenced in the diagnostic test done by the students at the beginning of the module. In this test, she got 4 points, while the other students got a scale among 7 to 10. So, it would be interesting to see the influence of some reading strategies to foster reading comprehension in this student since she was the only one who came back to study after four months. This student finished her last module with an average of 7/10, so it is probably that she catch up what she has to learn through these strategies.

Student B lives in Babahoyo too. She is a 25-year-old girl and she studies in the fifth semester of Nursing. She studied in a private school here in Babahoyo. Therefore, she has a better level of English in most of the skills. She has one sister, and her parents are teachers in a school. She has completed two levels of English with good grades because she had some basis from school. Although she is good at speaking and listening, reading and writing need to be improved. She has some text comprehension, but she needs to improve much more. In the Diagnostic test, she got 7.5 but in the following reading test she got 7. Thus, she was chosen for this case study since her previous knowledge has a good base, although she came back to study after two months. It would be interesting to see how the reading strategies apply in class could upgrade her comprehension skill. Through this case study, it is intended to know how reading strategies, in particular, think - Aloud enhance reading comprehension. Among these strategies can be mentioned:

In the Pre-reading process

- Activate prior knowledge to connect what they know with what they will learn, through questions, vocabulary activities, and predictions.
- The key word, this strategy help students activate vocabulary and knowledge before reading.
- K-W-L strategy to connect prior knowledge with what was learned. It can be used in the pre-reading process and the after reading process.

- Concept sort is a strategy where the reader has different words or ideas from a reading material and place them in different categories.

In the during process

- Skimming/scanning to identify main ideas and details in the text.
- Taking notes with the help of a story map.
- Comprehension questions can be used to confirm predictions during the reading or understanding of the text after the reading process.

In the After reading process

- Retelling the story, drawing pictures to summarize it.
- Comprehension questions
- Exit slip strategy. Students write on note cards or sheets of paper an important idea they learned, a question they have, a prediction about what will come next, or thought about a character, event, or another reading element. Fisher, D., and Frey, N. (2004).

B. Methodology

1. Data Collection

In this research the methodology included a description of the students who participate in it, the interview for both students and the procedure for the data organization. The collection of the data was carried out with the mixed method where the quantitative method was gathered from student A and student B with the application of similar activities, and instruments for assessments such as a diagnostic test at the beginning of the process, and true- false sentences. The qualitative method was gathered with an interview, and discussion activities. The procedure used to accomplish this research in the data organization process was made according to Anthony's quadrants which is a tool split in classroom measures, observation of the process and observation of product which are described below.

a. Classroom measure

The collection of data in this quadrant was done through a reading test with multiple choice questions applied to both students at the beginning of the course. This test has the purpose to know the level of reading comprehension students have developed at the beginning of this course.

Observation of process

The data gathered in this process was divided into three processes: the pre-reading, during reading, and after reading.

The gathering of information in the pre-reading process was done through think-aloud since this instrument assesses reading comprehension focus on the use of prior knowledge.

Another tool applied was an interview with both students to know information about needs and interest related to the reading skills. Although it is recommended to use this kind of instrument at the beginning of the course, it was applied after two weeks.

During the reading process, the collection of data was done through Strategies checklists, on account of this instrument allows gathering information about characteristics or behavior, reading skills, and students' engagement in the process. Anecdotal Records were also applied with the purpose to know the students' performance and what it is needed to improve.

Observation product

In the after reading process the collection of data was done through a retelling checklist to see how well the students comprehend the story. Another instrument implemented in this process was the self-assessment of reading strategies through a checklist with the purpose the student realizes what strategies were applied or not to improve reading comprehension. Another self-assessment tool used was the Exit Slip strategy to make likely students reflect on what they learned, how they feel, how it can be connected with what they have already learned, and so on.

2. Data Analysis: Pieces of evidence per student

a. A test

A test was administered at the beginning of the module to both students with the purpose to know the student's level in reading comprehension. The entry test illustrates the student's difficulties in some aspects of the text comprehension. This test was developed with ten multiple choice questions related to the passage. Student A got 5 out of 10 and Student B got 7 out of 10 correct answers. The options which caused difficulty to both students were the ones that require inference or deduction of what happened, so it means that comprehension of the text was not entirely developed during the reading process.

Fig.1: STUDENT A

Fig.1: STUDENT

a. First reading activity

The following week, another reading activity was made in class where the students were given a text about Health. Both students were given the same text, before the reading activity, there was a discussion session with some questions to introduce the topic. Student **A** expressed shorter or briefer ideas than Student **B** who used more vocabulary related to the topic and the sentence structured was well done. Fig. 2 has the transcription of the oral answer given by the students.

STUDENT A	STUDENT B
a. Do you think you have a healthy diet? Yes, I do.	a. Do you think you have a healthy diet? Yes, I eat vegetables and fruit. I do exercise.
b. How often do you eat things that you know are bad for you? No, sometimes I eat	b. How often do you eat things that you know are bad for you? I usually drink sodas and sometimes I eat snacks.
c. Has your diet changed since you were a child? If so how? Yes, eat many sugar	c. Has your diet changed since you were a child? If so how? Yes, I eat more vegetables and fruit.

Fig. 2 task 1. Discussion activity

Task 1. Discussion activity

In the following activity, both students have some phrases with bold words that the students had to guess the meaning from the context and match the words to some pictures. Then, they wrote in a graphic provided what they thought the words mean. Student A guessed two words from the context, and used poor vocabulary to write the meanings. On the other hand, Student B guessed the meaning of four words, and the meaning of the words were written with better vocabulary and grammar structure. Fig. 3 shows the task 3. With both activities.

Fig. 3 STUDENT A

Fig. 3 STUDENT B

During the reading of the text, both students complete a chart with the main idea and some details. Student A began to read the whole text, then read task 3 to do the exercise. A did not give a clear explanation for the main idea and details. Fig. 4 shows the answers.

Reading text

In the next task, the student had to identify the true and false sentences. Student **A** showed difficulty to understand the text since only three from the seven options were correct. Student **B** read task 3 first and began to scan the text to look for the main idea and details of the text. The ideas were expressed more clearly than the other student and **B** had five correct answers in the True –False task.

In the second part of the activity, Students had to write answers to two questions with opinions related to the topic. Student **A** answered partially, by contrary student **B**'s answers were much clearer. Fig. 4 shows the answers.

Fig. 4 Student A

Fig. 4 Student B

It was applied a reading strategy checklist to assess these reading Activities, with the purpose to analyze the main difficulties the students showed during the reading process. According to the information gathered, it was observed that Student A did not use reading strategies like prior knowledge, scanning, and skimming, rereads, make a prediction, and summarizing. Student B could activate prior knowledge, applied scanning and skimming to get the whole picture and details from the text, make predictions in the last stage of the reading, the same as a short summarize of the reading text.

According to the data gathered, Student **A** presented some difficulties in applying reading strategies, and the level of vocabulary is not high, but in spite of this fact, student **A** participate and try to talk even though some limitation. A possible situation that could influence these difficulties is the student's background since the previous language schooling was very poor.

Student **B** presented more application of reading strategies during the process. However, this student also has some difficulties with comprehension, the errors in the different tasks are less than the Student **A**. Maybe, it is because the student's B background in the previous language schooling was much better than Student **A**.

a. Interview

Because the results I got from the second reading activity were almost the same than the one got with the previous test, taking into account that reading is quite important in the acquisition of a foreign language, it was a need to know much more information about students' reading attitudes and strategies. So during the second week of classes an interview was conducted with both students to get the required information.

The information gathered shows that Student A has not got a habit to read in school or even at home, and it is considered a boring activity according to answer 1: "Nobody reads in my house" "it is boring." So as a result, some reading skills and strategies have not been developed. On the other hand, Student B likes to read adventurous, and fiction stories. **B** reads in Spanish a lot, and reading books in English is a goal for this learner. Thus, more reading skills and strategies have been developed much more than student

A. In this interview; the same eight questions were asked to Student **A** and **B**. Fig. 5 provides the interview.

Fig. 5 Interviews

a. Think aloud

After the data had been gathered in the previous activities, both students were called to be part of a reading class. Think aloud was applied together with anecdotal records to assess the process. Think-Aloud was used as a strategy because it helps students to think while they are reading by using modeling, coached practice and reflection. Roger Farr and Jenny Conner (2004). Every stage was first modeled by the teacher because it can be a little awkward if they do it independently since the very beginning. The teacher made some practice asking questions and giving models of strategies like skimming and scanning to get information. Then, the strategy of visualization was made, the students imagine the situation which was read to have a comprehension of it. In the example provided by the teacher the students read about how healthy a person could be if he or she runs or walks for 30 minutes every day, unlike with fifteen minutes of jogging. In this part, the teacher makes a visualization representing with pictures what was read and making notes. So, students can have a picture in their minds about the text, in such a way the passage is more understandable to the learner, as well as the students learn and apply a reading strategy. Once some modeling was done in the first session, the students had another lesson where they had to implement what they have learned.

In the first stage, both students were asked questions related to the topic to activate the prior knowledge.

The questions were:

ESTRATEGIAS DE THINK-ALOUD PARA MEJORAR LA HABILIDAD DE LECTURA

- a. Do you ever watch reality TV programs? If so which ones do you watch? If not, why don't you watch them?
- b. Would you like to appear in a reality TV program yourself? If so, which program? If not, why not?

Student **A** answered the questions well, and Student **B** gives an explanation about why the program is exciting. For the second question Student **A** answered clearly, but student **B's** summary was more explicit than Student **A**.

In the following step, the teacher asked:

What do you think you will learn about the topic?

Both students make predictions about what the theme of the text is going to be. Student A explained that according to the title it would be a passage about a reality show. Student B said that it is a reality show about performing the role of a singer and a magician in front of an audience. Both students scanned the text looking for clues to know the main idea. Fig. 6 shows this information.

Fig.6 Information about students 'questions

For the introduction of vocabulary, the students did a similar task to the one in the activity one. Student **A** and **B** had to explain the meaning of some words which were in bold in some sentences. Student **A** got five out six words, and Student **B** got six out six good meanings. So, it is evident that the level of guessing increased. During the observation of the students, it was seen that both use visualization strategy to do the vocabulary meaning. Fig.7 shows the task.

Fig. 7 Vocabulary activity

The students were provided with a KWL sheet where ideas about what was known about the topic, what they want to know and what was learned from the reading process. Fig. 8 shows the chart.

STUDENT A			STUDENT B		
K-W-L CHART: Complete the chart with your ideas about the topic:			K-W-L CHART: Complete the chart with your ideas about the topic:		
What I know	What I want to know	What I learned	What I know	What I want to know	What I learned
Realty shows are programs where people experience things when different situations.	I want to know about the part participate and this program.	I learned about the experience of the people to visit.	These programs are shows where people go to demonstrate their abilities in some thing	I want to know How these people can separate problem and do a good job	I learned about The separation and the wish to be the best

Fig. 8 KWL chart

Student A took notes to one side of the reading to clarify ideas about the vocabulary and the sentences to complete spaces in task 1. During the reading, Student A began to underline some words which were unfamiliar and tried to get the idea from the context. At the end of the reading with the notes taken from the chart about what was learned, and the ones written to one side of the reading. Student A answered the questions in Task 2. Under the questions, there was a box where the student had to draw some pictures that showed the main details of the story.

Student A drew five pictures which summarized the story. Lastly, the teacher asked Student A to use the pictures to tell the story. As it can be seen in fig.9, the notes that were written by student A to one side of the passage represented the meaning of the words which were analyzed. But there are others where the meaning was taken from the dictionary, but the most important thing is that the student could guess the meaning of some words from the context before looking in a dictionary. There are notes in the KWL chart that represent the details learned from the text. The information taken from the Anecdotal Record (Appendix 3), shows that student A could identify the main idea and details from the text through the application of some reading strategies. Therefore, the tasks were done better than in the previous activities, showing and increase in the level of reading comprehension. Fig. 9 shows the reading activities.

Fig.9 Student A's Reading activities

Student B underlined sentences that could answer the questions at the end of the text. This student wrote clearer meanings for the words guessed from context and the notes in the chart describe better details from the text. Student **B** did not need the dictionary to have the meaning, although it was not an exact meaning, it was very close and helped in the reading comprehension. Task was completed successfully, and in task two the answers were clearly stated, only one answer was incorrect. The pictures made to summarize the text represented quite well the story in different moments and were exposed clearly at the moment of telling the story.

Fig.9 Student B's Reading activities

The information from the Anecdotal record evidences. The improvement of Student **B** in reading comprehension tasks and the improvement in the application of reading strategies.

Lastly, a self-assessment of Think-Aloud checklist and a slip of paper with some questions were given to student **A** and **B** to make students do a self-assessment of the reading lesson, and realize how they have improved in reading comprehension. It works as a feedback for the student and the teacher since the questions are asked to know how much they learned, what they would like to read next, the way students feel about the process,

the questions or doubts they have and so on. (In appendix 4 shows Think-Aloud Checklist, Appendix 5 shows Self-assessment questions). The self-assessment results provided an overview of the process and the final product of both Students.

Student **A** applied reading strategies, which were new for this student. **A** could join the prior knowledge with the new one, could guess some words from context, could make predictions of what would happen in the story and got the main idea with details in the summary with pictures. So, the self-assessment showed that this student felt well to see that reading comprehension level was upgraded and showed interest to continue with this process because in one of the answers explained that it would be nice to continue reading in this way and proposed the possible topic for future reading. Student **B's** self-assessment showed that the process was done accurately and the strategies, which were already known by the student, improved much more since the process was developed with specific ideas and accuracy. The student increased not only the level of comprehension, but also the level of motivation to read more again, which have been forgotten for a while.

The data collected during the different activities and tasks in this reading process show the progress of both students from the beginning of the course with entry test until now. All this information becomes a profile for Student **A** and **B** which can be used for the students as a feedback to increase motivation. It is also a feedback for the teacher who can see the development of reading skills in the students. Moreover, with specific strategies like Think-Aloud, which integrate different tasks to develop students' reading comprehension, it can be developed other metacognitive skills like analyzing and synthesize.

The collecting of data from both students was done during the last two weeks. In a process of 10 hours. Although, it is needed much more time to get more evidence of the development the students' reading skills, during this short time, the students showed a change and improvement of the reading comprehension. So, a key point in this process of gathering data, and evidence from Student **A** and **B** was the participation and predisposition of the students to be part of this change in the learning process.

RESULTADO

Regarding to the activities applied before the Think-Aloud strategies the findings showed that:

ACTIVITIES	STUDENT A	STUDENT B
Pre-reading Activities		
Discussion	shorter and brifier ideas	use more vocabulary and sentence structure.
Vocabulary	guessed two words poor vocabulary	four words better vocabulary and grammar

ESTRATEGIAS DE THINK-ALoud PARA MEJORAR LA HABILIDAD DE LECTURA

During reading activities		
Complete a chart	No clear ideas	Clear main ide an details
True-False	3 out 7 correct sentences	5 out 7 correct sentences
	No use of reading strategies	Use some reading strategies: prediction- skimming and scanning

The results after the Think-Aloud strategies implementation were the following:

ACTIVITIES	STUDENT A	STUDENT B
Pre-reading Activities		
Interview	No habits to read	Likes to read Reads in English is a goal.
Vocabulary	Apply visualization strategy Guess meaning from context Got 5 out 6 correct words meaning	Apply reading strategies Got 6 out of 6 correct words meaning
During reading activities		
Complete KWL chart	Took notes Underline ideas Got details with reading strategies	Improve taking notes strategies Got clear main and detail ideas
Questions	Clear answers about the topic	Clear explanation with examples and details
	use of reading strategies	Upgrade reading strategies to get information
After Reading		
Summarize	Quite well pictures to summarize	Comprehension was upgrades with excellent pictures to explain the text
Self-Assessment		

DISCUSSION

The findings suggest that Think-Aloud strategies enhance reading comprehension in the students with a different language and cultural background. The results also provide some direction of how the process of these reading strategies could be carried out in class to upgrade the students' reading comprehension.

It could be seen that modeling the strategies by the teacher ensure students learn and the implementation of these strategies in their reading process. According to a research conducted by Gersten,R.; Fuchs,L. among others (2001) about teaching reading comprehension to students with learning disabilities, it was found that the modeling of these strategies not only help students to incorporate them in the reading practice but also encourage maintenance and transfer in different materials.

The results show that even though, the process was being developed recently, the students could begin to activate prior knowledge, apply the skimming and scanning strategies to look for main ideas, details to answer questions and visualization to get a picture of what is coming in the text and then make predictions in the pre-reading process. However, it is needed more vocabulary and grammar structure development to upgrade much more reading skills and reading comprehension. Nevertheless, it can be seen that Think-Aloud strategy in this first stage, enhance the students' reading comprehension.

The findings during the reading process suggest that in spite of the poor language background of the student A, she could take notes to get details and ideas to complete the chart and answer the questions. The student B upgrade quite well the implementation of reading strategies to summarize ideas and get the needed information. In spite of, Think-Aloud develops metacognitive skill such as analyzing and synthetizing, it takes time to apply the different tasks to make possible the maintenance the learning of these strategies. In the study conducted by Gersten,R.; Fuchs,L (2001) they recommend longer treatment duration to keep the students' effects.

Findings also show that feedback for the student and the teacher, and in this particular case, self-assessment allowed student **A** to be aware of the improvement in reading skills which increase motivation to continue reading even though it was the first time for her to do this kind of activities, she felt very well with them. For student **B**, an assessment made possible to realize what it was known, what she need to learn, to link known strategies with new ones to improve reading comprehension, but the most important, to be aware of the progress and take responsibility for it. As it is claimed by Routman, (1994) as cited by O'Malley and Valdez, (1996).p.100.

"Self-assessment, while not graded by the teacher, helps both teacher and student become aware of student's attitudes, strengths, and weaknesses in reading." However, self-assessment helps to increase motivation and interests in students since they are

aware of their weaknesses, it needs to be developed by the teacher step by step to let students take it seriously and incorporate it in their own learning process.

Lastly, for future studies, it would be relevant to apply an action research to the whole third level. The purpose will be to see if the Think-Aloud strategy helps to improve reading comprehension in most of the students in this level, as well as the interest to read more. Other important implication would be to see how interaction among students in a collaborative work could be enhanced through the application of this strategy can foster reading comprehension.

CONCLUSIONES

Reading comprehension is a skill which in some cases is difficult to develop, due to different factors like students' background, prior knowledge, lack of application of reading strategies, and so on. In the present case study, student A has a different cultural and language background than student B. A studied in a public school where the teaching of English is limited by many situations like a large number of students, and so on. According to Peregoy and Boyle, (2005), as cited in Kullman, N. PowerPoint, there are some areas of cultural difference like family structure, life cycles, discipline, religion, history, traditions and so on, which may affect students.' Learning and interpretation of texts.

Regarding to Think-Aloud strategy, there was an improvement in the process of reading in both students even though the poor background of Student A, she could improve her reading comprehension and interest in reading. Student B did not have the same difficulties, because this student had a good language background and some reading strategies like skimming and scanning. It is possible that the previous language background of this student could be a factor to improve much more than Student A. The process of prediction, analyzing the text, and summarizing got a better explanation in taking notes, guessing words from context and synthesizing ideas through pictures. O'Malley and Valdez, (1996).p, 120 said that Think-Aloud is a way to make students reflect out aloud about a text. These researchers also suggest modeling this strategy because it is new for the students and can be difficult. In the present study, teacher modeled the strategies, and not only ask the students to do the tasks. So, it was found a difference between the first and the second activity where the modeling of the teacher explained the functions better and increased the level of understanding of the strategy and consequently the comprehension of the text. Think- Aloud strategy answered the question about enhancing the reading comprehension level in students satisfactorily.

According to O'Malley and Valdez Pierce, (1996) PowerPoint. "Types of assessments available will require that students do something to show that they understand and can apply what they read." Assessment can be done through checklists of reading strategies which are lists of characteristics or behaviors, anecdotal records which focus on process

more than in the product; this instrument is ideal for assessing think- aloud strategy, and so on. The use of this different assessment tools offered a complete overview of the students' progress and what need to be developed yet for next reading lessons. Self-Assessment was a feedback for both students which increase the level of interest and motivation due to they found out the things they needed to improve and strategies they could apply to upgrade their comprehension in reading skill.

Another important issue in these findings is related to the prior knowledge activation through this strategy. Honig, Diamond & Glutohn are cited by Kelley & Clausen & Grace (2007) to say that "when readers predict they must engage with the text. They use their prior knowledge and the text to set up expectations of what will happen or what information the text will contain." (p. 79).

In this study, both Students have an improvement and more interest in the reading process with the application of prior knowledge activation. The students were engaged with the topic and showed a motivation to continue working in the reading process. It is evident that the teacher's modeling was crucial for the development of this strategy since students got a clear idea about what they had to do.

Therefore, it is important to suggest that modeling has to be well done during this process, to foster students' understanding. Another relevant aspect to be highlighted is to prepare a vocabulary activity before presenting the topic to help students in the text comprehension.

Despite the different methodologies or strategies that teachers could apply in class to achieve students' reading comprehension, it is important to keep in mind that the strategies that upgrade much more the learning process is the teachers' motivation to find the most outstanding strategies which could help their students according to their needs. Think-Aloud offer the opportunity to enhance reading comprehension implrmnte mutiplle strategies to keep the students' effects.

REFERENCES

1. Fisher, D., and Frey, N. (2004). *Improving Adolescent Literacy: Strategies at Work*. New Jersey:Pearson Prentice Hall
2. Gersten ,R., Fuchs, Lynn., Williams, Joanna P., and Baker, Scott. (2001). *Teaching Reading Comprehension Strategies to Students With Learning Disabilities*. American Educational Research Association. DOI: 10.3102/00346543071002279. <http://rer.sagepub.com/content/71/2/279>
3. Kelly, M. J., Clausen-Grace, N. (2007). *Comprehension shouldn't be silent*. Retrieved may 5, 2009, from http://books.google.com.co/books?id=mriwJujOzQAC&pg=PA138&dq=visualizing+as+a+reading+strategy&lr=&as_brr=3#PPP1,M1.
4. O'Malley and Valdez, (1996). *Authentic Assessment For English Language Learners*.U.S.A.: Addison-Wesley. p.120

5. Peregoy, S. F., Boyle, O., & Peregoy, S. F. (2005). Reading, writing, and Learning in ESL: A resource book for K-12 teachers. Boston: Pearson. Retrieved from Kullman.N. Powerpoints (2016)
6. Roger Farr and Jenny Conner. (2004). "Using Think-Alouds to Build Reading. Comprehension. Reading Rockets. Web. 25 Mar. 2015. <<http://www.readingrockets.org/article/using-think-alouds-improve-Reading-comprehension>
7. Routman, R.(1994). Invitations: Changing as Teachers and Learners K-12.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Portsmouth, N.H.: Heinemann.Retrieved from O'Malley&Valdez. (1996),p.100

